

A Study on Stress Management Among Pre-School Teachers with Special Reference to Tambaram Area

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M. Mohana Priya

*Ph.D. Full Time Research Scholar, Department of Commerce
Madras Christian College, East Tambaram
Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India*

Dr. Mrs. Tamilarasi Mailachalam, M.Com., M.Phil., Ph.D.,

*Head, Associate Professor & Research Supervisor
Department of Commerce, Madras Christian College
Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract

Stress is a universal phenomenon, which is prevalent in most of the people on Earth. It is faced in every sector. The study aims to find the reason for stress among Pre-school teachers. The respondents are from various schools located in Tambaram area. The different stress Managements techniques followed by Pre-school teachers and their top suggestions are mentioned based on their responses from the survey.

Keywords: Pre-School Teachers, Stress, Stress Management, Yoga and Meditation.

Introduction

Stress is a term which relates itself to a state of mental, emotional strain or tension resulting from situations where adverse demands are made. Stress can be from external or internal means. The external stress comes from the environment, psychological or social situations. The internal stress can be from illness or from a medical procedure. In this fast pace world, where we demand things to be taken care then and there, Stress has become a part of our day to day life. The stress is subjective and it changes from person to person. An instance which is stressful for a person may not have much impact on others. The stress is temporary. Our body is expected to return back to normal state. If the body is continued to stay in stress, it may take a toll, which may result in various illness and health issues over a period of time. Stress can be helpful sometimes, it is believed that our senses are heightened which can help avoid any accidents or meet deadlines by keeping our mind focused to overcome the after-effects which may arise due to our ignorance. Even Pre-school teachers are not exempted. The study aims to know about the reasons for stress and the stress management techniques among Pre-school teachers.

Causes of Stress

- Occupational demands
- Heavy Workload
- Career concern
- Work Under-load
- Poor working conditions
- Roles and Responsibility given
- Frustration
- Body Pain
- Personality
- Peer-pressure
- Lack of discipline among learners
- School Environment
- School Management practices.

Types of Stress

There are different types of stress. They are mentioned as follows.

Acute Stress: It is the most basic and a frequent form of stress. It is our body's most immediate reaction to a new challenge, and it fasters a flight response. It is also a kind of alertness when we exhibit when taking a task, which can be as simple as riding a vehicle. The Acute stress will not exhibit any lingering effects. Severe acute stress may result in post- traumatic stress disorder.

Episodic Acute Stress: When a person experiences an acute stress frequently, it results in acute episodic stress. Negative effects may be persistent in people with episodic acute stress.

Chronic Stress: If the acute stress is not resolved and begins to increase or last for long period of time, it begins a chronic stress.

Stress Management

Stress is unique to every person and can also cause a chain reaction. Men and women who work, show their work stress, as anger in front their family members and stress caused because of their family situations or personal reasons might be reflected in their work. Like stress, their impact on a person may also differ. Some people faint, some have headaches, insomnia, anger, changes in bowel moment, constipation etc...R Managing stress is much needed requirement for today's generation. For a happy and a peaceful life, stress management comes to the rescue.

Following methods can help to manage and relieve stress among Pre-School Teachers

- Disconnect from school related activities at home
- Do not work overtime
- Try not to be perfect every time
- Once a week, take time to plan your work for the entire week.
- Have a relaxed sleep, or quick naps if required
- Enjoy being with students
- Regular exercise and training
- Focused thinking
- Balanced diet
- Meditation and Yoga
- Control your anger

Objectives of the Study

- To study the various causes of stress among Pre-school teachers.
- To examine and suggests stress management techniques for pre-school teachers.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is limited to 50 pre-school teachers from 5 schools in Tambaram.

Research Methodology

Data collection: Primary data and Secondary data. Primary data is collected through questionnaire and the secondary data includes books, journals, research papers and internet.

Study Location: Respondents were selected from Tambaram area.

Sample Size: 50 Pre-school teachers from 5 schools.

Sampling Method: This study was conducted by convenience sampling method.

Table 1 Causes of Stress

Particulars	Rank
Work Overload	1
Job insecurity	2
Poor Working Conditions	4
No Participation in decision Making	7
School Environment	6
Peer & Pressure	5
Additional duties	3

From the study, it is inferred that Work overload (95%) holds the top ranking among the causes of stress. While the Job insecurity (87%), Additional Duties (80%), and the Poor working conditions (74%) holds the 2nd, 3rd, 4th ranking for the cause of stress among Pre-school teachers. Peer & pressure, school environment and no participation in decision making were also one among the reasons for stress.

Table 2 Stress Management Techniques Adopted

Particulars	Rank
Taking some “Me” Time	1
Physical exercise	5
Yoga & Meditation	6
Interacting with family members	3
Carry out hobbies	7
Balanced diet	4
Sleep	2

From the respondents, it is found that most of them prefer some “Me” time (83%) and sleep (77%) to get relieved from stress. They also interact with family members (75%) at the end of the day, and also have a balanced diet (60%) to take care of their health.

Research Findings & Conclusion

From the demographic profile, only females are preferred for the role of Pre-school Teachers and most of them belong to age group of 18 -30. Majority of the respondents are unmarried (60%) and the rest of them are married (40%). Most of the Pre-School teachers (44%) feel it is highly stressful for them because of factors like the poor working conditions, overtime, Additional duties, imbalance in maintaining the harmony between family and work and peer-pressure. In certain cases, responses include exploitation, forced to work overtime were also the reasons for Stress. Even though they are qualified teachers, they felt they were not paid enough. The prime reason which causes stress, should be eradicated rather than concentrating only on the stress management techniques. Hence forth, School management should revise the salaries for Pre-school teachers on a yearly basis considering their performance with a good hike.

Many of the respondents were aware about the benefits of the adopting techniques like yoga and meditation. But they do not spend enough time to relieve their stress by doing so. Awareness programs can be conducted to encourage Pre-school teachers to take up the practice of yoga and meditation in their day to day lives. The management must take several initiatives to timely interact with staffs and help the Pre-school teachers to advance and stabilize their career, for a stress free work environment, which can benefit both the institution and the teachers as well.

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